

Programme Services v2

Deliverable 3.3 – Programme Services v2

Prepared by: Startup Wise Guys and Business Angels Europe

Description

Full list of services published on our website and as a brochure for consultation, including the description of services for the second half of the project.

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Table 1. Project information

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Table 2. History of Changes

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	28.03.2025	First draft of Programme services	Ilze Graubina (SWG)
v0.2	18.04.2025	Second draft of Programme services	Sara Anselmo (BAE)
V0.3	24.04.2025	Finalized draft of Programme services	Ilze Graubina (SWG)
VF	25.04.2025	Final review of the Programme services	Marta Fernández Bernabeu (SPLORO)

Table 3. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name	Description
SWG	Startup Wise Guys	Name of a legal entity
BAE	Business Angels Europe	Name of a legal entity
Q&A	Questions and answers	Session type
MVP	Minimum viable product	A version of a product with just enough features to be usable by early customers who can then provide feedback for future product development.
KPIs	Key performance indicators	Type of performance measurement.
1on1	One on one	Type of the session where the startup meets one expert
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats	SWOT analysis is a strategic planning and strategic management technique used to help a person or organization identify Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to business competition or project planning.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	The General Data Protection Regulation is a European Union regulation on information privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.
IP	Intellectual Property	Intellectual property is a category of property that includes intangible creations of the human intellect.
ICP	Ideal Customer Persona	A detailed profile of the perfect customer.

Disclaimer:

Funded by the Horizon Europe Programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement number 101100515. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the EISMEA can be held responsible for them.

Abstract:

The presented document is the EmpoWomen “Programme services” which lists all activities planned in the EmpoWomen Programme and includes a detailed description of services.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. PROGRAMME OVERVIEW	7
2. PART 1 – BUILD & SCALE.....	9
2.1 Time Frame:.....	9
2.2 Introduction:.....	9
3. PART 2 - INVESTMENT READINESS FOR WOMEN IN DEEP TECH.....	12
3.1 Time Frame:.....	12
3.2 Introduction:.....	12
Annexes	14
Annex 1. Programme Activities	14

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Programme timeline Cohort 2.....	7
Figure 2. Programme Part 1.....	9

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Project information.....	2
Table 2. History of Changes.....	3
Table 3. Abbreviations.....	3
Table 4. Programme Session Types.....	11
Table 5. Programme Activities to be delivered in Part 1.....	14
Table 6. Programme Activities to be delivered in Part 2.....	41

1. PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

EmpoWomen is a two-year programme (2024-2025) funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme. It aims to address the underrepresentation of women in the deep-tech sector, particularly in emerging European countries. Through open calls, 25 women-led startups will be selected to participate in a specialized acceleration programme co-designed by Startup Wise Guys and Business Angels Europe. Each startup will receive tailored support, services, awards, and €45,000 in equity-free funding.

The programme consists of two cohorts, each running for six months. It is designed to empower female founders by equipping them with the necessary resources and expertise to build and scale their deep-tech startups successfully and become investor-ready.

Timeline

Programme timeline during 6 months

Figure 1. Programme timeline Cohort 2

Cohort 2 of the EmpoWomen programme begins on March 3rd with a Welcome Session, followed by a deep dive into defining startup KPIs and goals for the programme, as well as the development of their deep-tech solutions.

The first part of the programme, "How to Build and Scale a Deep-Tech Startup," focuses on key aspects of the startup journey, including problem definition, pitch presentation, sales, legal considerations, and fundraising. This phase will conclude with the Progress Day event, where startups that meet the programme's criteria will showcase their products and progress from the first three months to an online audience.

Following this event, startups will report on their achieved goals and KPIs before transitioning to the next phase.

The second part of the programme, "Investor Readiness," is designed to prepare startups for fundraising. Participants will receive in-depth training on working with investors, structuring fundraising efforts, and handling legal aspects to ensure full investment readiness.

The programme will conclude with an onsite Demo Day, where startups that successfully meet the programme's completion criteria will present their products and key achievements from the six-month journey. The final step will be reporting on the goals and KPIs achieved during the second phase.

Table 5. Programme Activities to be delivered in Part 1 and Table 6. Programme Activities to be delivered in Part 2 in the Annexes section provides an overview of all events and activities scheduled throughout the six-month programme. It includes detailed descriptions of each session, covering aspects such as duration, session type, key learning objectives, and timing.

2. PART 1 – BUILD & SCALE

2.1 TIME FRAME:

From March 3rd until May 30th; when the second part of the programme, the investment readiness programme, starts. The first phase of the programme ends with an online event, the Progress Day, where the startups present their projects and the improvements done to the consortium, investors and the lead coaches.

2.2 INTRODUCTION:

The core of the first part of the programme consists of eight weeks of content, also known as learning weeks, with each week dedicated to a specific topic.

Part 1

First part of the programme consist of 8 content weeks - **How to build and scale women-led deep tech startup**

Figure 2. Programme Part 1

- **Week 1 - Welcome Week**

During the initial week, participants are encouraged to familiarize themselves with the programme’s structure, objectives, and available tools. They should explore programme materials, add the event calendar to stay informed about upcoming online sessions, and actively engage with fellow participants via Slack, where they will receive the latest updates and announcements.

The primary focus of this week is to clarify the criteria for successful programme completion. Startups will gain a clear understanding of all required deliverables, reporting expectations, and the key milestones needed to ensure they are fully prepared for the journey ahead.

- **Week 2 - Purpose and Values**

This week focuses on the fundamental questions surrounding a startup's purpose. Participants will define their company's mission, vision, and culture, establishing a strong foundation for their entrepreneurial journey.

- **Week 3 - Pitching and Product**

This week's focus is on gaining insights into effectively communicating the product and its value proposition. Emphasis will be placed on understanding the problem each startup's product solves, as this is the first step toward successful sales and market penetration.

- **Week 4 - Product and Planning**

This week focuses on refining the product to align with market demands and customer needs. Participants will explore experimentation methods and learn how to build or plan a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) that effectively addresses key customer pain points and stands out in the market.

- **Week 5 - Staying Strong**

This week focuses on navigating the challenges of startup life by building personal resilience and adopting sustainable growth strategies. Participants will explore methods to maintain peak performance and stay prepared to tackle obstacles as they arise.

- **Week 6 - Sales**

This week focuses on an intensive crash course covering sales, marketing, and branding strategies. Participants will refine their sales approach while ensuring their brand identity stands out in the marketplace.

- **Week 7 - Fundraising**

This week focuses on enhancing the ability to communicate effectively with potential collaborators and investors. Participants will explore key financial metrics and strategies essential for securing investment and successfully scaling their startups.

- **Week 8 - Legal basics**

This week focuses on addressing critical legal matters essential for a startup's compliance and protection. Topics will include business registration, GDPR compliance, and strategies for mitigating legal risks.

Table 4. Programme Session Types

Type	Description	Duration	Participants
Welcome session	Group session held in Zoom	1.5 hours	Startups, Partners, Programme Lead
Programme Goals & KPIs	Group session held in Zoom	1 hour	Startups, Programme Lead
Q&A	Group session held in Zoom	1 or 1.5 hours	Startups, expert, moderator
Peer to Peer	Participants are divided in small groups (3 to 5 startups) in the Zoom breakout rooms	1 hour	Startups, moderator
Webinar+Q&A	Group session held in Zoom	1 or 1.5 hours	Startups, expert, moderator
Fireside chat	Group session held in Zoom	1 hour	Startups, speakers, moderator
Pitch Drills 1on1 mentoring session	1on1 session held in Zoom, but any participant can attend as a listener	20 min per startup	Startups, expert, moderator
1on1 mentoring session	Individual mentoring session held in Zoom or Google Meets	Up to 60 min	Startup, mentor
Progress Day	Group session held in Zoom	2.5 hours	Startups, moderator, partners, external experts
Demo Day	Held onsite	6 hours	Startups, moderator, partners, external experts

3. PART 2 - INVESTMENT READINESS FOR WOMEN IN DEEP TECH

3.1 TIME FRAME:

From June 2nd until July 31st, 2025; followed by August break; and final two sessions delivered between 1st – 12th September 2025. Demo day to take place in October 2025.

3.2 INTRODUCTION:

Part 2 main content of the programme will be delivered by Business Angels Europe (BAE) and will be led by Jenny Tooth OBE, VP Diversity at BAE and CEO of UK Business Angels Association, who is a leading expert in gender focused investing.

The purpose of this 11-week programme will be to provide an in-depth understanding of how to successfully prepare and position the deep-tech business for attracting investment. The programme is designed to build on the learnings gained during the first part of the programme, focusing on business development to complement the course content and mentoring provided through Part 1.

In the first two weeks of Part 2 of the programme, alongside the initial webinars, BAE will offer each participating start-up a dedicated 30-minute one-on-one feedback session on their Finance and Investment Plan assignment, which will have been submitted in the final week of May. The sessions are designed to deliver tailored, actionable feedback to help refine each start-up's financial planning and investment strategy. Start-ups will be able to book time slots that suit their availability via a shared booking system.

The course will cover the topics as set out below, providing insight on how to develop an effective strategy to approach investing both for women who are approaching funding for the first time and enable them to build upon any existing experience they have had in seeking funding to date. Each module will be designed to take the entrepreneurs through each step of the investment process, from developing an effective investment proposal and investment toolkit, successful pitching, follow up engagement with investors, preparing for the due diligence process, to investor negotiation including valuation. The modules will also provide extensive insight into the legal and contractual process, including deal structuring whilst also enabling insight into their relationship with the investors post deal, governance and strategic planning for future funding rounds.

The weekly modules will be presented in the form of a live webinar enabling direct learning and engagement whilst enabling immediate Q&A opportunities to discuss any specific aspects with the tutors.

The webinars will be delivered by highly experienced Angel investors selected from BAE's own membership, who are all established Angel investors in startups and early-stage businesses, many with deep domain experience in technology, including deep-tech and key relevant sector application. The majority of the Angel tutors will be women Angel investors who will be drawn from BAE's Women Angel Leaders Task force. They will provide deep insights into the potential challenges and issues encountered by women in deep-tech, while recognising their specific concerns in seeking funding. In addition, BAE will draw on legal experts to deliver the webinars on legal and contractual documents and technical insights.

A key element of the design of this programme that differentiates it from other similar programmes is that it provides extensive insights and understanding among the women entrepreneurs of how investors think and approach the investments they make. This gives the women entrepreneurs specific understanding of how to approach and engage investors, understanding their requirements and needs for information and how to effectively work with them to achieve a successful outcome.

Each webinar will be recorded so that the entrepreneurs can access the webinar at any time in a recorded version and this will also include access to additional materials, templates, links and further tools and resource, which will be shared on Slack in the dedicated channel. Each webinar will be accompanied by a knowledge test which the female entrepreneur will be asked to complete, which enables them to check their understanding and learning and go back to key elements in the webinar to reinforce their knowledge and understanding. The entrepreneurs will be supported throughout by their SWG Lead coach or mentor who will help to reinforce their understanding and address any issues raised in the programme modules or content.

The programme will culminate in the Demo Day, which will be jointly organised by SWG and BAE, where the skills and knowledge gained by the women in deep-tech across both parts of the programme will be demonstrated, while also enabling feedback and advice from both investors, mentors and coaches.

In addition, the cohort of women entrepreneurs will have the opportunity to attend a dedicated online pitch presentation and investor engagement session during September. This session will be organised by BAE and the women entrepreneurs will each present their business and have a 10 minutes personal feedback and mentoring session from a group of specially invited BAE investors, all experienced in investing in deep-tech.

During Part 2, SWG will deliver four peer-to-peer sessions, one one-on-one check-in session to ensure startups are on track with their deliverables, and one group session just before Demo Day to provide clarity on logistics and the event format.

In addition, at the beginning of September, there will be organized a Mentor Day where startups will have the opportunity to meet experts from various industries and backgrounds, offering valuable insights and guidance to support the founders on their journey.

Annexes

ANNEX 1. PROGRAMME ACTIVITIES

Table 5. Programme Activities to be delivered in Part 1

Activity	Welcome session - “Welcome and Goal Setting”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 1 - “Welcome and Goal Setting” - Week of March 3rd, 2025		
Description¹			
<p>The Welcome Session is an online event conducted via Zoom, bringing together all participants, the Programme Lead, and invited Programme partners.</p> <p>Purpose</p> <p>The session aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce participants to the Programme and each other. • Explain the Programme structure, rules, and expectations. • Provide guidance on Programme tools and resources. <p>Session Details</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1-2 hours, depending on participant questions. • Led by: Programme Lead. <p>Key Takeaways</p> <p>By the end of the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain a clear understanding of the Programme structure, rules, and mandatory activities. • Learn how to navigate Programme tools and access essential information. • Understand Programme expectations, key performance indicators (KPIs), and deliverables. • Connect with Programme partners and fellow participants. 			
Activity	Webinar and Q&A “Programme Goals & KPIs	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 1 - “Welcome and Goal Setting” - Week of March 3rd, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session, conducted via Zoom, brings together all participants and the Programme Led to clarify the Programme’s goals, key performance indicators (KPIs), and requirements.</p> <p>Purpose</p>			

¹ Including duration and speaker/mentor/ coach

The session aims to:

- Provide a clear understanding of the Programme’s objectives and success criteria.
- Outline the mandatory KPIs and milestones that participants must meet.
- Explain the requirements related to payments and deliverables.

Session Details

- **Duration:** 1-2 hours, depending on participant questions.
- **Led by:** Programme Lead.

Key Takeaways

By the end of the session, participants will:

- Understand the Programme’s goals, KPIs, and evaluation criteria.
- Be aware of the mandatory requirements, including deliverables and payment-related objectives.
- Gain insights into best practices for meeting Programme expectations.

Learn how to track and report progress in alignment with Programme standards.

Activity	Peer to Peer “Myths and Stereotypes of female-led deep tech startups”	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 1 - “Welcome and Goal Setting” - Week of March 3rd, 2025
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Description

This interactive online session, conducted via Zoom, brings together all participants and the Programme Lead for a peer-to-peer discussion on the challenges and perceptions surrounding women-led deep tech startups.

Purpose

The session aims to:

- Foster open discussions about common myths and stereotypes of female founders in the deep tech industry.
- Encourage participants to share experiences, insights, and strategies for overcoming biases.
- Strengthen connections among Programme participants to create a supportive network.

Session Details

- **Duration:** 1 hour.
- **Led by:** Programme Lead.
- **Format:** Participants will receive a PDF guide outlining the session structure, discussion topics, and key questions in advance.

Key Takeaways

By the end of the session, participants will:

- Identify and understand common stereotypes about women-led deep tech startups and strategies to challenge them.
- Share and discuss real-life experiences, challenges, and solutions from their entrepreneurial journeys.
- Build meaningful connections with fellow participants, fostering collaboration and support.

Gain motivation and confidence to navigate the deep tech ecosystem and grow their businesses.

Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 1 - “Welcome and Goal Setting” - Week of March 3rd, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week is dedicated to ensuring that all startups have access to the essential information and tools needed to successfully begin the Programme.</p> <p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform, which serves as the central hub for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Programme Information - Including guidelines, structure, and successful completion criteria. • Learning Materials - Pre-recorded videos covering key topics for each week, providing essential insights and guidance. <p>This platform will be a key resource throughout the Programme, ensuring participants have everything they need to stay informed and on track.</p> <p>Each video includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A description of the week's focus and objectives. • Educational content relevant to the topic. • A call to action with recommended tasks, templates, and next steps. • Engagement & Knowledge Check. <p>After watching the weekly videos, participants must complete a Knowledge Check form. This form includes questions based on the video content, allowing us to track engagement and ensure participants are actively following the material.</p> <p>Videos to Watch in Week 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem-Solving Mindset - Strategies to approach challenges from different perspectives. • Mentoring: Top 10 Tips - Best practices for preparing for one-on-one meetings with mentors and coaches. • Alumni Testimonials - Insights and inspiration from past SWG participants about their experiences and key takeaways. <p>Key Takeaways</p> <p>By the end of this week, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the Programme structure and where to find key information. • Learn how to effectively engage with mentors for maximum impact. <p>Gain insights from past Programme participants to optimize their experience.</p>			

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 1 - “Welcome and Goal Setting” - Week of March 3rd, 2025		
Description			
<p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform, where they will find weekly assignments designed to support their progress. This week’s assignments are mandatory and focus on accessing Programme materials and providing essential information to the programme’s managers. Completing these tasks is crucial for fulfilling Programme requirements.</p> <p>Week 1 Assignments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill in the Startup Entry Form - This is the first step in adding your startup’s information to the Programme database. • Add the Programme Calendar - Ensures all scheduled sessions and events are visible in your personal calendar. • Join Slack - The primary communication tool to stay updated on activities, announcements, and important events. • Sign Up for Airtable - Gain access to learning materials, Programme resources, and essential information. • Review the Goal & KPIs Setting Template - Available in Airtable under Resources section along with Goal setting guidelines and examples. This template will help participants complete the first Deliverable, which must be submitted by the end of Month 1. <p>By completing these assignments, participants will be fully prepared to navigate the Programme efficiently.</p>			
Activity	Webinar and Q&A “Goal Setting”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 2 - “Purpose and Values” - Week of March 17th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session, held via Zoom, brings together all participants, the Programme Lead, and an expert coach to guide startups through the Goal and KPIs setting process helping them define achievable, measurable, and realistic objectives.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn how to effectively use the Goal Setting Template to structure your startup’s objectives. • Understand the key differences between KPIs and tasks to ensure clear, actionable planning. • Explore the SMART goal framework to set measurable success indicators • Prepare for your first one-on-one session with your assigned Lead Coach, who will support your progress throughout the Programme. <p>Session Details</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1.5 hours. • Led by: Programme Lead and expert coach. <p>Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions.</p>			

Activity	1on1 sessions with assigned Lead coach	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 2 - "Purpose and Values" - Week of March 17th, 2025		
Description			
<p>These individual coaching sessions are conducted online via Zoom or Google Meet and provide dedicated time for each startup to discuss their Programme goals, KPIs, and business growth objectives with their assigned Lead Coach.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure startups define clear, measurable, and realistic goals for successful Programme completion. • Provide guidance on aligning business objectives with Programme requirements. • Offer personalized feedback and support in the goal-setting process. <p>Session Structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 30-60 minutes, depending on the participant’s questions. • First Session: Startups must prepare and present a draft version of their goals and KPIs for review. • Follow-up Sessions: Regular check-ins will be scheduled to track progress and refine goals. • Final Goal Review: At the end of Month 1, a review session will be held with a Programme Lead and a Lead coach to validate the final goals. Upon confirmation from the Project main partners Sploro the startup will receive the first €5,000 funding. • Ongoing Support: Even after receiving initial funding, 1-on-1 coaching sessions will continue to ensure that the startup stays on track toward achieving its goals. • Long-Term Coaching Support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Goals are required for Part 1 and Part 2 of the Programme. <p>The Lead Coach will be available for up to 10 individual coaching sessions over 6 months to provide ongoing support.</p>			
Activity	Peer to Peer "Purpose and Values"	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 2 - "Purpose and Values" - Week of March 17th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session, held via Zoom, brings together all participants and the Programme Lead for an interactive discussion on the purpose and values of female-led deep-tech startups.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a platform for participants to reflect on their personal and company values. • Explore how personal values influence company culture, decision-making, and performance. • Foster discussions on challenges and opportunities specific to female-led deep-tech startups. • Encourage participants to learn from each other’s experiences and build valuable connections. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead 			

- **Format:** Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand the importance of personal and company values in shaping a startup’s success.
- Reflect on how personal values align with business goals and work performance.
- Begin defining or refining your startup’s core values to guide its growth and impact.

This session provides a unique opportunity to connect with like-minded entrepreneurs, share experiences, and strengthen the foundation of your deep-tech business.

Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 2 - “Purpose and Values” - Week of March 17th, 2025		

Description

This week focuses on discovering the purpose, mission, vision, and culture of your startup. A key part of the week is goal setting and an introduction to pitching to help participants align their business objectives with a strong foundation.

Participants will have access to the Airtable platform, where they can find pre-recorded videos covering the week’s topics. Each video includes:

- A description of the weekly theme within the Programme.
- Educational insights on the topic.
- A call to action with recommended tasks and templates to apply the learning.

After watching all the videos for the week, participants must complete the Knowledge Check form, which includes questions related to the topics covered. This allows Programme managers to track engagement and ensure participants have reviewed the content.

Videos to Watch:

- Setting Goals - How to identify achievable and reasonable Goals & KPIs.
- Purpose and Values - Understanding the importance of purpose and values and how to align them with business goals.
- The Power of Strong Culture - How to develop a strong company culture and why it is crucial for startup success.
- Team: You Are My Army Now - The importance of identifying critical roles within a startup and evaluating whether the team has the right people in place.
- Stages of a Startup - An overview of different startup stages and key actions required for success.
- Deconstructing Your Business - A framework to analyse and challenge existing business assumptions to ensure the startup is creating the right value for the right market segment.
- Introduction to Pitching - The different types of pitches startups need to master, with practical advice on how to prepare an effective pitch.

Key Takeaways:

After completing this week’s materials, participants will understand:

- Goal Setting; How to set Goals & KPIs effectively.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose and Values; The importance of aligning personal and company values. • The Power of Strong Culture; How a well-defined company culture contributes to business and team success. • Building a Strong Team; How to structure a team to achieve results. • Startup Stages; Identifying the stage of development their deep-tech startup is currently in. • Deconstructing Your Business; How to analyse and refine the startup's business model. <p>Introduction to Pitching; How to structure and deliver a three-minute investor pitch.</p>			
Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 2 - "Purpose and Values" - Week of March 17th, 2025		
Description			
<p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform, where they will find assignments related to Week 2 topic. These assignments are provided in Microsoft Word or PDF format and include detailed descriptions, instructions, and examples to help participants complete the tasks effectively.</p> <p>This Week's Assignments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work on Goals & KPIs for the Programme - Finalize Goals and KPIs using the provided template. The template includes instructions and examples to help define Business, Technology, Product, and Investment goals, along with a mentorship plan. • Define Your Purpose - Work on both personal and company purpose using the provided exercise document designed to help founders reflect on their core motivations and mission. • Establish Company Values - Define personal and company values using the provided template. Participants should also ask their teammates to contribute to align the company's core values. • Lean Canvas Exercise - Create a Lean Canvas for the deep-tech business or review and update an existing one. The provided template includes instructions and guiding questions to help refine the business model and value proposition. <p>Start Working on Your Pitch Deck - Begin developing a 3-minute investor pitch deck or review and refine an existing one. A structured template is provided to help craft a compelling and concise presentation.</p>			
Activity	Finalizing Goals & KPIs - 1on1s with Programme Lead and Lead coach	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	No new content week - Week of March 24th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week will be dedicated to the finalization of Goals & KPIs, and no new content will be unlocked on Airtable.</p> <p>Each startup will participate in a 1-hour session via Zoom with the Programme Lead and Lead Coach to ensure that their Goals & KPIs are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective • Measurable • Aligned with the Programme criteria 			

During the session, each startup will need to present the latest version of their Goals & KPIs. Based on the feedback received, they will be required to update their plan and submit it to the main project partner, Sploro, for final review and confirmation.

This is a critical milestone in the Programme, as startup growth and progress will be evaluated based on these goals. Successful achievement of the set Goals & KPIs, along with sufficient supporting evidence, will determine eligibility for further grant funding:

- €20,000 after Part 1
- €20,000 after Part 2

Activity	Webinar and Q&A session “Problem definition”	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 3 - “Pitching and Product” - Week of March 31st, 2025
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Description

This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and the expert coach.

Purpose:

The goal of this session is to analyse and refine each startup's problem statement, ensuring it:

- Strongly aligns with product-market fit.
- Resonates with potential clients.
- Clearly defines a market need worth solving

Session Details:

- **Duration:** 1.5 hours
- **Led by:** Programme Lead and expert
- **Format:** Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions.

Key Takeaways:

After the session, participants will:

- Understand problem definition techniques and their importance.
- Learn how to determine if a problem is worth solving and has market fit.

Gain insights on how to shape their problem statement to better target potential clients.

Activity	Peer to Peer session “Pitch Practice”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 3 - “Pitching and Product” - Week of March 31st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <p>The goal of this session is to provide startups with a platform to practice their pitch in a collaborative environment. By pitching to peers, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain constructive feedback from fellow founders. • Improve their presentation skills. • Better understand how other deep tech startups position themselves <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <p>After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insights into other startups’ products and pitching styles. • Practice delivering their pitch in a supportive setting. <p>Receive valuable feedback to refine their presentation.</p>			
Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 3 - “Pitching and Product” - Week of March 31st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week focuses on defining a strong problem statement that resonates with customers and refining how the startup’s product provides a meaningful solution. A solid problem statement is the foundation of product-market fit and a key element in a compelling pitch.</p> <p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with pre-recorded videos covering this week’s topics. Each video includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview of the topic. • Educational content on problem definition, customer profiling, and pitching. • Actionable steps with relevant templates and assignments. <p>At the end of the week, participants must complete the Knowledge Check form to validate their</p>			

understanding of the material.

Videos to Watch:

- Problems to Solve - How to craft a solid problem statement.
- There Are No Problems, Only Solutions Waiting to Be Found - How to test if your solution truly addresses the identified problem.
- How to Identify Your Ideal Customer Profile - Understanding target customers and their existing alternatives.
- Powerful Pitching - A series of four videos covering:
 - Crafting a compelling hook
 - Defining product, market, business, and company narrative

Key Takeaways:

After completing this week’s material, participants will:

- Learn how to identify and frame problems as opportunities.
- Understand methods for defining their ideal customer profile, a critical step in startup success.

Gain an introduction to “Powerful Pitching”, covering the structure and key elements of a 3-minute investor pitch, including real-world examples.

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 3 - “Pitching and Product” - Week of March 31st, 2025		
Description			
<p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform, where they can find assignments related to this week’s topics.</p> <p>Assignments are provided in Microsoft Word, Excel, or PDF format, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task descriptions. • Examples for reference. • Guidelines to help participants complete each exercise effectively. <p>These tasks are optional but highly recommended, as they provide practical exercises to help participants refine their deep tech business and product strategy.</p> <p>This Week’s Assignments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SWOT Analysis - Define the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for your deep tech startup. A template is provided to structure the analysis effectively. • Defining the Ideal Customer Profile - Identify your startup’s target audience and potential paying customers. A template with guiding questions will help refine customer segmentation. <p>Building or Refining the Pitch Deck - Start creating a pitch deck or assess an existing one to ensure it aligns with Programme requirements and industry standards. A document with instructions and key questions is provided to help craft a compelling pitch.</p>			

Activity	Webinar and Q&A session “MVP and Product Building”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 4 - “Product and Planning”- Week of April 7th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and the expert coach.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <p>The goal of this session is to discuss MVP development and product-building stages, ensuring that startups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the key phases of MVP and product development. • Identify their current stage and necessary next steps. • Receive expert guidance on technical challenges and product strategy. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1hour • Led by: Programme Lead and expert coach • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <p>After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the stages of MVP and product development. • Identify their startup’s current stage and the next steps for growth. <p>Gain insights and support from an experienced technical expert.</p>			
Activity	Peer to Peer session “Tough Questions”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 4 - “Product and Planning”- Week of April 7th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <p>The goal of this session is to provide participants with the opportunity to discuss and tackle the "tough questions" that every startup founder faces, particularly when building a product in the deep-tech industry.</p> <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide. 			

<p>Key Takeaways:</p> <p>After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn how to effectively address difficult questions and make critical decisions. • Be challenged to think about different aspects of their business and personal values to prepare solid responses for future inquiries. • Gain insights from peers on handling tough questions. <p>Be better equipped to answer challenging questions commonly asked by investors.</p>			
Activity	Webinar “Women and complex tech solutions”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 4 - “Product and Planning” - Week of April 7th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and invited female speaker from the deep-tech industry.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <p>The goal of this session is to address the unique challenges women face when building deep-tech startups and complex tech solutions. Participants will gain insights from female role model who have successfully navigated the industry and engage in discussions on the technological aspects of deep-tech product development.</p> <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead and guest speaker from the deep-tech industry • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <p>After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insights into overcoming challenges when building deep-tech solutions. • Hear success stories and learn from female role models in deep tech. <p>Discuss technological aspects of deep-tech product development with industry experts.</p>			

Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 4 - "Product and Planning"- Week of April 7th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week’s focus is on refining the product to ensure it is unique, valuable, and aligned with customer needs.</p> <p>Access to Learning Materials</p> <p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform, where they can watch pre-recorded educational videos related to this week’s topic. These videos provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A description of the week’s theme. • Educational insights into product development. • Calls to action with suggested tasks, templates, and next steps. <p>After watching the videos, participants must complete a Knowledge Check form to ensure engagement and comprehension of the content.</p> <p>Videos to Watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a Value Proposition - Understanding what a value proposition is and why customer insights matter. • Uniqueness and Competition Analysis - Identifying competitors and crafting a unique market offering. • Experimenting - Learning the importance of testing and iteration in startup success. • Minimum Viable Product (MVP) - Defining the key components of an MVP and determining how closely it should resemble the final product. • Effective Planning - Mastering planning techniques to prioritize product development effectively. <p>Key Learning Outcomes:</p> <p>By the end of this week, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to develop a strong value proposition. • Learn how to differentiate their startup from competitors. • Gain knowledge on experimenting and pivoting based on validated insights. • Build or refine their MVP development plan. <p>Master effective planning and prioritization for product development.</p>			

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 4 - "Product and Planning"- Week of April 7th, 2025		
Description			
<p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with assignments designed to reinforce this week’s learning topics.</p> <p>Assignment Format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available in Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, or PDF format. • Includes task descriptions with examples for better understanding. • Optional but encouraged for skill development and business growth. <p>This Week’s Assignments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discovery Interviews - A template with guiding questions to help startups conduct effective customer interviews and gain insights into customer problems. • MVP and Product Development Plan - A document with guiding questions and advice on planning an MVP, identifying priorities, and defining key product development steps. <p>Effective Planning - A resource with guiding questions and strategies for managing Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) effectively.</p>			
Activity	Webinar “Pitching”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 5 - "Staying Strong" - Week of April 14th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and the expert coach.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <p>The goal of this session is to guide participants in building a strong pitch deck and preparing a 3-minute investor pitch for their deep tech startup.</p> <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1.5 hours • Led by: Programme Lead and expert • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <p>After the session, participants will:</p>			

- Learn how to structure pitch deck slides effectively.
- Develop a compelling 3-minute investor pitch speech.

Review good and bad examples of pitch slides for better understanding.

Activity	Peer to Peer “Life hacks”	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 5 - “Staying Strong” - Week of April 14th, 2025
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Description

This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.

Purpose:

The goal of this session is to provide participants with an opportunity to share and discuss "life hacks" that help startups perform better - both in developing their business and maintaining personal well-being to sustain optimal energy levels.

Session Details:

- **Duration:** 1 hour
- **Led by:** Programme Lead
- **Format:** Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide.

Key Takeaways:

After the session, participants will:

- Learn practical strategies to improve startup performance and productivity.
- Gain insights from fellow founders on maintaining balance and energy levels.

Discuss real-world experiences and best practices for efficiency and well-being.

Activity	Webinar “Deep-tech Project and Time Management”	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 5 - “Staying Strong” - Week of April 14th, 2025
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Description

This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and invited female deep-tech speaker.

Purpose:

The goal of this session is to address and discuss the challenges women face when building deep-tech startups and other complex tech solutions, particularly from a project planning and team management perspective. The session will cover time management challenges and provide role model speaker who can share positive examples of women successfully building deep-tech products.

<p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <p>After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insights on how to efficiently plan projects and manage time when building complex deep-tech solutions. <p>Hear inspiring stories and practical advice from female role model who have navigated the challenges of building deep-tech products.</p>			
Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 5 - “Staying Strong” - Week of April 14th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week’s focus is on sustaining startup momentum and pushing the business to the next level. The aim is to equip participants with tools to stay energized, manage founder responsibilities, and tackle crises while maintaining focus and building a strong startup culture.</p> <p>Access to Learning Materials</p> <p>Participants will have access to pre-recorded videos related to the week’s topics on Airtable, offering educational insights and actionable steps. After watching the videos, participants are required to complete a Knowledge Check form to evaluate engagement and confirm they have absorbed the material.</p> <p>Videos to Watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimal Energy: Educational content on how to apply the PERFORM methodology to stay mentally and physically strong. • Staying Focused - Tips on how to remain focused and prioritize actions that lead to success. • Founders' Roles & Responsibilities - Two videos explaining the founder’s role and responsibilities in a startup. • How to Talk About the Product in Times of Crisis - Guidance on what a startup founder should say and do when facing crisis moments. • Crisis Management - Educational video on how to manage the team and build a strong company culture that can weather crises. <p>Key Learning Outcomes:</p> <p>After watching the videos, participants will learn:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to stay mentally and physically strong and maintain optimal energy throughout the startup journey. • How to plan effectively and set priorities that align with business growth. • What a startup founder’s role entails, and what they should or shouldn’t do in this leadership 			

position. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to communicate with external resources and customers about the product during a crisis. How to manage the team spirit, build a resilient culture, and stay on top of the game even in challenging times.			
Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 5 - “Staying Strong” - Week of April 14th, 2025		
Description			
Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with assignments designed to reinforce this week’s learning topics.			
Assignment Format: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available in Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, or PDF format. • Includes task descriptions with examples for better understanding. • Optional but encouraged for skill development and business growth. 			
This Week’s Assignments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimal Energy - A template with instructions to analyse energy distribution and assess whether there is a healthy balance between work, personal life, and startup growth. • Restaurant Activity - A creative exercise where each team member envisions their startup as a restaurant, helping to identify key brand attributes, market positioning, and ensure team alignment on core business aspects. Crisis Planning - A structured template guiding startups in creating a core action plan for navigating potential crises, identifying risks, response strategies, and defining team roles in uncertain situations.			
Activity	Q&A session “Sales”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 6 - “Sales” - Week of April 21st, 2025		
Description			
This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and the expert coach.			
Purpose: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide insights into best practices and techniques for sales in deep tech startups. • Address participants' sales-related challenges with expert guidance. • Equip startups with actionable strategies to improve their sales approach. 			

<p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead and expert • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain a clear understanding of effective sales techniques and best practices. • Receive expert advice tailored to individual startup sales challenges. <p>Improve sales strategies and approaches based on professional insights.</p>			
Activity	Webinar and Q&A session “Ideal Customer Persona”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 6 - “Sales” - Week of April 21st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead and invited expert coach.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce the concept of Ideal Customer Persona (ICP) and explain its importance for startup success. • Break down the key elements that define a strong ICP. • Highlight common mistakes and misconceptions when identifying ICPs. • Explore how multiple ICPs can exist within one business model and how to manage them. • Show how defining an ICP supports better marketing and sales strategies. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what makes an effective Ideal Customer Persona and why it matters. • Learn how to avoid typical ICP-related pitfalls. • Gain clarity on how to tailor marketing and sales efforts based on a defined ICP. <p>Access a practical analysis template to help apply the ICP framework to your own startup.</p>			

Activity	Peer to Peer session “Brand”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 6 - “Sales” - Week of April 21st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide participants with peer feedback on their startup brand identity. • Evaluate brand elements such as logo, colour schemes, and overall impression. • Discuss how branding influences perception and positioning in the deep tech industry. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insights into how others perceive their brand and its visual elements. • Understand the impact of branding on customer and investor perception. • Identify potential improvements to strengthen their startup’s brand identity. 			
Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 6 - “Sales” - Week of April 21st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week’s focus is on sales and branding, ensuring that startups develop a strong market presence and refine their outreach strategies. The aim is to equip participants with tools to validate their ideas, connect with potential customers, and create a brand that stands out.</p> <p>Access to Learning Materials</p> <p>Participants will have access to pre-recorded videos related to the week’s topics on Airtable, offering educational insights and actionable steps. After watching the videos, participants are required to complete a Knowledge Check form to evaluate engagement and confirm they have absorbed the material.</p> <p>Videos to Watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idea Validation & Traction - Educational content on how startups can validate their ideas and gain traction in the market. • Leverage Your Network - Practical advice on how to build and use connections to generate new 			

leads.

- How to Reach Out to Contacts - Best practices for engaging with potential customers and initiating conversations.
- Brand: The Basics - Strategies for developing a brand that resonates with customers and clearly represents the startup’s purpose.

Key Learning Outcomes:

After watching the videos, participants will learn:

- How to validate their startup idea and demonstrate traction in the market.
- Where to find potential customer contacts and how to effectively reach out.
- Best practices for engaging with new leads and converting them into customers.

How to build a brand identity that differentiates their startup and aligns with its values.

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 6 - “Sales” - Week of April 21st, 2025		
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Description

Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with assignments designed to reinforce this week’s learning topics.

Assignment Format:

- Available in Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, or PDF format.
- Includes task descriptions with examples for better understanding.
- Optional but encouraged for skill development and business growth.

This Week’s Assignments:

- Idea Validation & Traction - A template to help startups build a sales pipeline and set clear sales goals.
- How to Leverage Your Network - A step-by-step guide on quickly identifying and reaching out to valuable contacts.
- How to Reach Out to Contacts - A template for creating an effective customer outreach strategy.
- Minimum Viable Brand - A document with guiding questions and exercises to differentiate the startup from competitors and develop a strong brand.

A Rose by Any Other Name - A resource with instructions on ensuring the startup’s brand name is unique and aligned with its identity.

Activity	1-on-1 session with Pitch expert	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	No new content week - “Pitch Drills Week” - Week of April 28th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week is dedicated to refining and perfecting the 3-minute investor pitch deck. Startups will have the entire week to work on their pitch, ensuring it effectively communicates their value proposition, market opportunity, and business potential.</p> <p>Startups will follow a structured process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial Recording: Each startup will record their 3-minute investor pitch and share it with the expert for review. • 1-on-1 Feedback Session: Startups will present their pitch live in a 1-on-1 session with the expert, receiving direct feedback and suggestions for improvement. • Revisions & Final Submission: After incorporating the feedback, startups will update their pitch and record a final version for submission. <p>This process ensures that each startup develops a clear, compelling, and investor-ready pitch, preparing them for future fundraising opportunities.</p> <p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the invited expert coach, and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide each startup with an opportunity to present their 3-minute investor pitch with slides. • Receive individual feedback and suggestions from the expert and Programme Lead. • Allow participants to learn from peers by observing other pitches and feedback sessions. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 20 min per each startup. • Led by: Programme Lead and the expert coach. • Format: Individual 20 min time slots for each startup. • Participation: Other startups can join to listen and learn. • Mandatory: Attendance is required for eligibility to present on Progress Day. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain expert feedback to refine and improve the 3-minute investor pitch. • Learn from other startups’ mistakes and best practices. • Strengthen presentation skills. 			

Activity	Q&A session “Fundraising”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 7 - “Fundraising” - Week of May 5th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and the expert coach.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer participant questions regarding investments and funding challenges. • Offer guidance on securing investment and preparing for investor conversations. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead and expert coach • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive expert advice and support tailored to their startup's fundraising needs. <p>Learn effective strategies for securing investment and managing investor relations.</p>			
Activity	Peer to Peer Session “Communication”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 7 - “Fundraising” - Week of May 5th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate discussions on effective communication strategies for startups. • Identify current challenges in communicating with potential customers, investors, and collaborators. • Share best practices for improving clarity and impact in startup messaging. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insights into communication challenges and strategies for overcoming them. • Learn how to refine messaging for different audiences, including investors and customers. 			

Exchange feedback with peers to improve startup communication effectiveness.			
Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 7 - “Fundraising” - Week of May 5th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week’s focus is on robust communication, ensuring participants develop strong leadership skills, effective engagement techniques, and financial acumen to support their startup’s growth.</p> <p>Access to Learning Materials</p> <p>Participants will have access to pre-recorded videos on Airtable, covering key communication and financial topics. After watching the videos, participants must complete a Knowledge Check form to assess engagement and comprehension.</p> <p>Videos to Watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership Communication - Strategies for effective communication with partners, colleagues, and teams. • Communication Basics - Techniques to engage with teams and foster strong collaboration. • Providing Feedback - Best practices for delivering constructive and impactful feedback. • Receiving Feedback - How to accept and implement feedback effectively. • Holistic Strategy - Methods to assess and improve employee experience within a company. • Never Enough - Understanding key factors that contribute to long-term success and personal growth. • Startup Finance - Guidance on creating a financial plan and understanding critical financial components. • SaaS Metrics - Insights into customer acquisition costs, lifetime value, and churn rates. <p>Key Learning Outcomes:</p> <p>After watching the videos, participants will learn:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective communication methods to strengthen leadership and team dynamics. • How to engage and motivate teams for better collaboration. • The importance of providing and receiving feedback to drive continuous improvement. • How to evaluate employee experiences and implement necessary changes. • Strategies for long-term startup and team growth. • How to build a financial plan and track startup financial health. <p>How to analyse key business metrics to ensure financial viability and investor readiness.</p>			

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 7 - “Fundraising” - Week of May 5th, 2025		
Description			
<p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with assignments designed to reinforce this week’s learning topics.</p> <p>Assignment Format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available in Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, or PDF format. • Includes task descriptions with examples for better understanding. • Optional but encouraged for skill development and business growth. <p>This Week’s Assignments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial Plan - A template to help startups create a structured financial plan. <p>Finances - A task prompting startups to brainstorm and analyse their sources of income and expenditures.</p>			
Activity	Q&A session “Legal”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 8 - “Legal”- Week of May 12th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants, the Programme Lead, and the expert coach of the week.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide participants with insights into key legal aspects relevant to startups. • Discuss essential legal documents, GDPR compliance, intellectual property, and other legal considerations. • Allow participants to ask questions and receive expert advice on legal topics <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead and Coach of the week <p>Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions.</p> <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the most important legal documents every startup should have. • Basic knowledge of GDPR compliance. <p>Opportunity to ask legal-related questions and receive expert guidance.</p>			

Activity	Group session “Progress Day preparations”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 8 - “Legal”- Week of May 12th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online group session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide participants with a clear understanding of Progress Day and its significance. • Explain the next steps in the programme and how to prepare for Part 2. • Address any questions regarding the event and preparation requirements. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear instructions on Progress Day expectations and format. • Detailed guidance on preparing for the next phase of the programme. <p>Opportunity to clarify doubts and ensure readiness for the upcoming stage.</p>			
Activity	Video materials	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 8 - “Legal”- Week of May 12th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This week’s focus is on understanding legal fundamentals, GDPR compliance, and intellectual property (IP) protection.</p> <p>Access to Learning Materials</p> <p>Participants will have access to pre-recorded videos related to the week’s topics on Airtable, offering educational insights and actionable steps. After watching the videos, participants are required to complete a Knowledge Check form to evaluate engagement and confirm they have absorbed the material.</p> <p>Videos to Watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Term Sheets - Educational content explaining what a term sheet is, why it is needed, and key terms 			

- such as valuation, liquidation preferences, vesting, options, anti-dilution, and pro-rata rights.
- Registering Your Business - Guidance on selecting the right country for business registration and understanding legal entity structures.
 - Basics of GDPR - Overview of GDPR regulations, data protection principles, and why compliance is essential for startups.
 - Knowing Your IP: Introduction - Explanation of intellectual property, why it is important, and which business assets can be protected.
 - Protecting Your IP - Practical advice on conducting an IP audit and securing intellectual property rights.
 - How to Deal with Lawyers - Best practices for working with legal professionals while managing costs effectively.

Key Learning Outcomes:

After watching the videos, participants will learn:

- The purpose and structure of term sheets, and how to maintain control over their startup.
- The importance of choosing the right country for business registration.
- How GDPR impacts startups and the necessity of early-stage data protection planning.
- The fundamentals of intellectual property and how to safeguard business assets.

Best practices for working with legal professionals without overspending.

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 8 - "Legal"- Week of May 12th, 2025		
Description			
<p>Assignments</p> <p>Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with assignments related to the week’s topic.</p> <p>These assignments are available in Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, or PDF format and include task descriptions with examples to help participants understand how to complete them effectively. The assignments are optional but provide practical exercises to develop key skills and strengthen their deep tech business and product.</p> <p>This Week’s Assignments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR Mapping Your Data Guidelines - Template with instructions to help startups identify and understand their data assets. • GDPR Mapping Template - Fill in a template to assess data protection strategies and ensure compliance. <p>Term Sheet - Document with guiding questions and a task to help participants prepare for future investor negotiations.</p>			

Activity	Assignments	Lead partner	SWG & BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 9 - "Progress Day" - Week of May 19th, 2025		
Description			
<p>Progress Day is a key event where startups demonstrate what they have learned during Part 1 of the programme. This online session, conducted via Zoom, includes all participants, programme partners, the Programme Lead, and invited mentors and external coaches. The session lasts 2 to 2.5 hours, depending on the number of startups pitching.</p> <p>Each startup will deliver a 3-minute investor pitch, followed by 5 minutes of Q&A with the audience. This session provides an opportunity to refine presentation skills and receive valuable feedback from experts and peers.</p> <p>After Progress Day, startups will have one week to review the available online content, complete their Finance and Investment Plan development homework, and prepare for Part 2 of the programme, which will focus on Investor Readiness over the next 11 weeks.</p>			

Table 6. Programme Activities to be delivered in Part 2

ACTIVITY	Webinar "Introduction to the Investment Readiness Programme"	Lead partner	BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 10 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of June 2nd, 2025		
Description			
<p>This session will be held online and will be delivered live through Zoom, led by Jenny Tooth and will be recorded. It will last up to 1 hour.</p> <p>The session will cover the following topics:</p> <p>Introduction to the overall investment readiness programme and what will be covered in the weeks ahead. This will include considerations that the cohort may want to make about their own business and finance needs, which will be based on the task that they have carried out during May on their finance and investment plan, as well as needs and consideration of their experiences and lessons learned so far.</p> <p>The session will include an opportunity for participants to ask questions about the investment readiness programme and to each say a little about their fundraising experience so far, namely in terms of challenges and successes.</p>			
ACTIVITY	Webinar "The core basics"	Lead partner	BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 10 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of June 2nd, 2025		
Description			
<p>This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.</p> <p>It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the investment market and equity supply chain • What finance is right for you • What are business angels, angel syndicates and their added value • Identifying your funding strategy from angel to scale-up <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.</p> <p>This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of the overall funding landscape and investment market; what are the different areas of finance that are right for your business and stage of development; and how to develop the core elements of a funding plan and strategy.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat,</p>			

as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Webinar “Understanding the needs and requirements of investors and how to develop an effective investment proposal”	Lead partner	BAE
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Timeline	Programme Week 11 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of June 9th, 2025
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Description

Demo Day and Engagement with Investors

ACTIVITY	Webinar “Identifying your investment needs and presenting your investment proposal”	Lead partner	BAE
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Timeline	Programme Week 12 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of June 16th, 2025
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Description

This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.

It will cover the following topics:

- Developing your investment proposition and financials
- Establishing and presenting your investment needs

The session will build on the previous week’s session and is designed to enable the participants to build their skills in developing an effective proposition that sets out clear investment level financial projections, based on a clear understanding of their business growth strategy, their traction achieved so far and understanding their financial needs. The aim will be to provide clear insights on how to move from a business plan to an investment plan by gaining an in depth understanding of how investors will evaluate financial projections and their financial needs as a deep-tech business and what they will need to consider and think about when presenting to investors.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website

links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Peer to Peer session “Building credibility in male dominated industry ”	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 12 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of June 16th, 2025
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Description

This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.

Purpose:

- Explore strategies for building self-confidence and credibility as a female founder
- Discuss challenges faced by women in the deep tech industry
- Share experiences and best practices for gaining recognition and authority

Session Details:

- **Duration:** 1 hour
- **Led by:** Programme Lead
- **Format:** Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide.

Key Takeaways:

- Learn effective techniques to build confidence and establish credibility.
- Gain insights from peers on overcoming industry biases.

Identify actionable steps to strengthen your position as a leader in deep tech.

ACTIVITY	Webinar “Developing your investment readiness toolkit”	Lead partner	BAE
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Timeline	Programme Week 13 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of June 23rd, 2025
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Description

This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours .

It will cover the following topics:

- Developing your toolkit to attract investors
- What data and information investors want to see

This session will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to develop an effective and comprehensive toolkit to meet the requirements of investors and prepare for direct engagement with investors. The toolkit will include the financial plan and proposition; executive summary; pitch presentation (short and long versions); other data and documentary requirements to address investors information needs. Each element will be carefully defined and explained and with relevant examples for women in deep-tech.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Webinar “Making a winning pitch and how to develop your skills in engaging with investors”	Lead partner	BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 14 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of June 30th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.</p> <p>This session will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making your winning pitch to Investors • Successful presentation skills • Engaging with investors <p>This will include a detailed overview of how to successfully structure and deliver a compelling, informative and inspiring presentation to investors, including practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.</p> <p>This session will build on the previous session on developing an investment tool kit and is designed to give an in-depth understanding of the pitch as a central mechanism to present and showcase the business and investment opportunity. Key elements of what makes for a compelling and inspiring pitch, both in the structure and delivery, will be presented. This will include key elements and skills such as personalisation; story telling; creating tension and holding attention. Considerations of both structure content, but also direct delivery skills and key presentation tips and strategies, will be discussed. Insights will also be given on what makes a poor pitch or fails to attract investors and what to avoid in both content and presentation. A further key element to be covered will be how to respond to investors questions immediately following the pitch and initial due diligence carried out by investors at this stage and how to prepare to respond to investors questions. Key examples, as well as an opportunity for practical demonstrations, will be carefully</p>			

defined and explained and featured with relevant examples related to the needs of women in deep-tech.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Peer to Peer session "Financial Literacy and Funding Strategies"	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 14 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of June 30th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate a discussion on financial literacy and funding strategies for deep tech startups. Exchange ideas on creating financial concepts and securing investment. Share best practices for managing startup finances and attracting funding. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Duration: 1 hour Led by: Programme Lead Format: Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain insights into different financial models and funding approaches. Understand how peers are structuring their financial plans and securing investments. <p>Identify strategies to strengthen financial literacy and improve fundraising efforts.</p>			
ACTIVITY	Webinar "Post pitch preparing for due diligence"	Lead partner	BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 15 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of July 7th, 2025		

Description				
<p>This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.</p> <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The topics covered will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging with investors after the pitch • Preparing for due diligence: scope and purpose and how to respond to investors needs <p>This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to engage with investors in the period following the pitching session. It will aim to provide a clear understanding of how to effectively follow up with investors following the pitching session and to ensure investor interest. The second half of this session will be designed to give an in depth understanding of how to prepare for and engage in the due diligence process. This will include understanding the core elements of the business and investment proposition that will be looked at in depth and ensuring that they have gathered all of the relevant data evidence and information to address the investor’s concerns and issues in a timely, effective and confident way. It will include an understanding of how investors conduct due diligence, particularly at Angel and early-stage investment level and their approach to the core areas: the team and the founders, the business model, the market, the technology product and applications, the corporate structure, the legal issues and the financials. Illustrations will be provided to show how information should be formatted and presented. Guidance will also be given on how to approach detailed questioning and inquiries, helping entrepreneurs prepare thoroughly for the process. The importance of using this opportunity to gain deeper insight into the investors - and assess whether the relationship is likely to be successful and valuable - will be emphasised.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.</p> <p>The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.</p> <p>Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.</p>				
ACTIVITY	Webinar “Negotiations”		Lead partner	BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 16 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of July 14th, 2025			
Description				
<p>This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.</p> <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights</p>				

from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a woman deep-tech entrepreneur.

The topics covered will be:

- Understanding how to value your business: Art or Science?
- Understanding potential deal structures
- How to effectively negotiation and understand what investors require and what works for you

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to value your business for investment purposes and how to understand the approach that investors are likely to make in understanding the valuation of your business and the methodologies that can be applied and that this frequently is more of an art than a science and the importance of creating a flexible approach to negotiation. The session will be devised to provide practical understanding and parameters for valuation in relation to an early-stage scaling deep-tech business, whilst having a clear understanding of the approach and requirements of investors including examples, case studies and practical tips on how to justify and present the valuation to the investor, whilst understanding the points of negotiation and conflict.

A final aspect of this session will be to gain an overall understanding of how to approach the structure of the deal in relation to the valuation and finance needs and the benefits of both direct equity deals, or those based on convertible loan notes and advanced security mechanisms that establish the valuation over a period of time, as well as the benefits and the negatives of the different approaches in the context of a valuation and successfully accessing investment.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Peer to Peer session "Negotiation and Deal making"	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 16 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of July 14th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss techniques for successful negotiation and deal-making in deep tech startups. • Share experiences and strategies for negotiating with investors, partners, and other stakeholders. • Explore best practices for structuring deals and managing the negotiation process. <p>Session Details:</p>			

- **Duration:** 1 hour
- **Led by:** Programme Lead
- **Format:** Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide.

Key Takeaways:

- Learn effective negotiation tactics tailored to the deep tech industry.
- Gain insights into structuring deals that benefit both parties.

Understand the key considerations when negotiating with investors and partners.

ACTIVITY	Webinar “Understanding the termsheet and achieving a successful outcome”	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 17 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of July 21st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.</p> <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The topics covered will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the key elements of the termsheet • What can go wrong with the deal <p>This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to engage with investors to achieve a termsheet as an indication of the commitment to make an investment and how to successfully manage the negotiation process. The aim of the session will be to give an in depth understanding of the key terms of the timesheet and how this relates to the due diligence process, building on the previous session; how to respond to the details information and evidence requirements to ensure that investors are satisfied; providing a clear understanding of some of the pitfalls and challenges in achieving a successful and satisfactory timesheet. Notably, this session will aim to equip the women in deep-tech with a clear understanding of how to confidently negotiate, work with and gain the outcome of the type of investment and level of investment they require, whilst at the same time understanding that the process may break down and their opportunities to walk away from the process if this does not feel right.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat,</p>			

as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	1on1s with Programme Lead	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 17 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of July 21st, 2025
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Description

This session will be held online via Zoom with each participant individually.

Purpose:

- Provide individual check-ins with each startup to assess their progress throughout the programme.
- Review completed and outstanding mandatory activities.
- Offer a dedicated space for startups to ask questions and receive personalized guidance.

Session Details:

- **Duration:** 1 hour with each startup
- **Led by:** Programme Lead
- **Format:** Informative discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions.

Key Takeaways:

- Clear understanding of what has been achieved and what remains to be completed.
- Personalized feedback and support tailored to each startup's journey.

Opportunity to clarify any uncertainties and align expectations for the remainder of the programme.

ACTIVITY	Webinar "Understanding the legal contractual process and documentation to structure the deal"	Lead partner	BAE
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Timeline	Programme Week 18 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of July 28th, 2025
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Description

This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Legal expert in structuring Angel and early-stage deals, together with an Angel Investor, on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.

This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech

entrepreneur.

The topics covered will be:

- Understanding the legal process and the core documents
- The shareholders agreement
- Articles of association

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of the legal and contractual aspects of closing the deal, providing a detailed understanding of the core documents; what the various terms and requirements mean; and that the contractual requirements and protections are clearly understood. It will aim to provide understanding of what is their relationship to the investors post investment, the protections on both sides and ensure that they are confident in their knowledge of the relevant documentation and technical aspects.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Peer to Peer "Cultivating Leadership Skills"	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 18 - "Investor Readiness" - Week of July 28th, 2025		
Description			
<p>This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate discussion on leadership development tailored to deep tech founders. • Share techniques for building and strengthening leadership skills. • Explore strategies for effectively leading a growing team in a complex innovation-driven environment. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration: 1 hour • Led by: Programme Lead • Format: Interactive discussion with guided questions provided in a PDF session guide. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what leadership looks like in a deep tech startup setting. • Learn practical approaches for improving leadership effectiveness. 			

Gain insights from peers’ experiences and strategies for leading teams through growth and change.			
ACTIVITY	Webinar “Finalising the deal and key legal considerations”	Lead partner	BAE
Timeline	Programme Week 19 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of September 1st, 2025		
Description			
<p>This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Legal expert in structuring Angel and early-stage deals, together with an Angel Investor, on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.</p> <p>This session will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The topics covered will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalising the investment deal • Understanding the cap table • Governance and reporting <p>This session will build on the previous session on legal documents and focuses on closing the deal. It will be designed to cover the final elements of consideration, both contractually and in terms of the ongoing relationship with investors and why these areas are important for the ongoing relationship between the women in deep-tech team and their investors and for the future development of their business. This will include understanding the cap table as a core component of the final shareholders’ agreement, that sets out the number of shares held by the founders and other existing investors in the business, as well as the shares to be issued to new investors, and why this is important for ongoing control and incentives for the founders and team. The session will also talk about the key areas in the shareholders agreement about governance and which will set out the investor’s role on the board and what expectations there are of reporting and providing strategic information and why it is important to finalise these issues prior to closing the deal.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.</p> <p>The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.</p> <p>Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.</p>			
ACTIVITY	Mentor Day	Lead partner	SWG
Timeline	Programme Week 19 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of September 1st, 2025		
Description			

This session will be held online using the Zoom platform.

Purpose:

- Provide startups with the opportunity to receive expert feedback through dedicated 1-on-1 mentor meetings.
- Enable startups to ask focused questions and receive tailored advice from experienced professionals.
- Support startups in refining strategies, solving challenges, and identifying next steps.

Session Details:

- **Duration:** 45 minutes per mentor meeting
- **Lead by:** Programme Lead
- **Format:** Individual 1-on-1 sessions in Zoom breakout rooms
- **Mentor Selection:** Startups will choose up to 4 mentors from a pool of 30+ experts prior to the session

During the Session:

- Startups will lead the conversation by asking questions relevant to their business.
- Mentors will provide feedback, share expertise, and suggest next steps or best practices.

Key Takeaways:

- Receive actionable feedback from industry experts.
- Gain clarity on specific challenges and opportunities.

Build valuable connections with experienced mentors.

ACTIVITY	Webinar “Making the most of your investor post deal and planning for next stage funding”	Lead partner	BAE
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Timeline	Programme Week 20 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of September 8th, 2025
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Description

This session will be held online, will be delivered live by an experienced Angel Investor on Zoom and will be recorded, lasting 2 hours.

This session will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deep-tech entrepreneur.

The topics covered will be:

- Making the most of your investors post investment
- Planning further funding rounds

This session will focus on the relationship with investors after the deal is done and will be designed to provide an in-depth understanding of how to effectively work with investors to get the most out of their experience, expertise, introductions, knowledge and support which provides important added value to the business post investment. The session will provide insights and case studies of how to make the investor relationship work effectively, specifically the do’s and don’ts of how to work together. A further key part of the session will be to discuss the planning of the next round of investment as the business grows and at what point after the first investment to start to plan for accessing next stage investment, the role of the investor and how to position your business for next stage funding.

This will provide a final session on the investment process, before the final Demo Day session at the end of the course when the women entrepreneurs will be engaging with the investors.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions written into the chat, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

The session will be followed by a short knowledge test available online, to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements.

Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on Slack, including wider website links, additional data, case studies and templates.

ACTIVITY	Demo Day preparations	Lead partner	SWG
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Timeline	Programme Week 20 - “Investor Readiness” - Week of September 8th, 2025		
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Description			
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This online session will be conducted via Zoom with all participants and the Programme Lead.

Purpose:

- Provide participants with a detailed overview of the Demo Day format and expectations.
- Share important logistical and organizational information.
- Announce the official Demo Day lineup.

Session Details:

- **Duration:** 1 hour
- **Led by:** Programme Lead
- **Format:** Informative discussion with a Q&A session to address participants' questions.

Key Takeaways:

- Clear understanding of Demo Day flow, timing, and structure.
- Awareness of presentation expectations and audience composition.

Confirmation of each startup’s place in the Demo Day lineup.

ACTIVITY	Demo Day and Engagement with Investors	Lead	SWG &
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		partner	BAE
Timeline	October 2025		
Description			
<p>This session, conducted in-person, will be jointly delivered by SWG and BAE, providing opportunities to the entrepreneurs to directly present to investors, alongside other key players from the EmpoWomen Programme partnership. BAE will mobilise a group of investors with core experience and expertise in investing in deep-tech and with a specific focus on involving women Angel investors.</p> <p>Purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer startups the opportunity to pitch live on stage to a curated group of investors and an external jury. • Showcase the progress and achievements made throughout the six-month programme. • Create visibility for female-led deep tech startups and connect them with investors, including women Angel investors mobilised by BAE. • Celebrate the conclusion of Part 2 of the programme and award top-performing startups. <p>Session Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Format: In-person event • Led by: Programme Lead • Duration: Approx. 6 hours (including setup, pitching, and closing) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pitching segment: Up to 3 hours ○ Full event: Up to 6 hours <p>Pitching Format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pitch time per startup: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 minutes for investor pitch ○ 1 minute to highlight key achievements from the programme ○ 5 minutes for Q&A with the jury • Evaluation: Startups will be scored by the external jury, and 3 winning startups will be announced and awarded monetary prizes based on final evaluations. <p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain visibility and exposure to a panel of investors with deep-tech expertise. • Showcase growth, traction, and strategic direction to key stakeholders. <p>Compete for recognition and funding in a high-impact finale event.</p>			